

The Impact of Social Welfare Policies on International Relations

Anna Beatriz de Sousa Chaves Clovis¹

^{a1}Department of Social Work, Universidade Federal Fluminense (UFF), Niterói 24210-201, Brazil, analive123@hotmail.com; annasousa@id.uff.br

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Abstract.

The aim of this article was to analyse the effects of social welfare policies on the international relations. The purposes of this article referred to the perspectives of change in the world, the role of social welfare policies, and how they directly impacted the maintenance of international organizations and governments, as well as the process of internationalization and cultural integration to improve multilateral relations in contemporary times. Social welfare policies play a crucial role in the development of society. This paper provided new insights into the impact of social welfare policies. Research and data were analyzed, which object to the association between these policies and global relations. The results indicated the practices of these policies, as well as their effects which directly impact on social and global development. This study revealed a more critical approach that involves the benefits of these policies in favor of social and global progress. This impact was observed through the action of international organizations that are also responsible in the elaboration of social policies, transnationalism that comes from the globalization process, in addition to new global trends such as: the ideas of social impact represented by the "social impact jobs" and the concept of sustainable development and its association with the practices of social welfare policies.

Keywords. social welfare policies, international relations, internationalization, cultural integration, global development.

1. Introduction

Interestingly, social welfare policies, have a very profound and impactful characteristic. Some studies have shown a great relationship between social welfare policies and a major breakthrough in international development. [1] This analysis aims to promote a more complementary scenario for social welfare policies and, consequently, demonstrate the new perspectives in the current international conjuncture.

These new perspectives on social welfare policies reveal mainly a confrontation related to the transformations generated by the process of globalization coming from capitalism, which directly affect the way of life of society. However, this global transformation ultimately increases the implications generated by the social issue, which can be very detrimental to the progress of social welfare policies. [2] Basically, social welfare policies are in charge of addressing inequalities, meeting human needs, and guaranteeing the rights of the ruling class. Not only do they promote the general well-being of the population, but their practice also provides a much deeper purpose, which has been increasingly associated with the international development.

1.1 Basic Human Needs

Fig. 1 - Global level of investment of social welfare policies on basic human needs. [3] [4]

1.2 Social Progress Globally

Fig. 2 - Map of investment levels in social welfare policies – global results [3] [4]

Initially, in the first statistic [3], for example, the practices of these social welfare policies in different countries showed a higher priority to basic human needs, which are: nutrition and basic medical care, water and sanitation, shelter, and personal safety, which are considered to be the main investment factors in international relations.

On the other hand, in the second statistic [3] it was shown that there is a high rate of inequality between the areas of development where social welfare policies are implemented around the world. From figure 2, it can be noted that, there is a higher priority of investment of these policies in industrialized and developed countries, while social welfare policies do not manifest the same level of attention in emerging or underdeveloped countries and need to be better put into practice. [4]

Salas [5] emphasized the trend on the development of these social welfare policies in developed countries. According to him, demographic assistance was extended to countries as development aid, since this was the type of activity that was already understood by most developing countries. Finally, this study focused on analyzing how these policies are interconnected, what are their main effects and how they correlate with the progress of contemporary social development, mainly with the advent of internationalization and cultural integration.

Taken together these results, the studies draw attention to the importance of social welfare policies, which positively impact global relations. For this reason, social welfare policies must be developed to address inequalities and guarantee the rights of the ruling class. These findings add substantially to our understanding of the expansion of these policies around the world. Given these points, more ideas of social welfare were implemented, either by social groups or by political entities. However, in this study, due to the popularity of the social welfare policies, there was a striking international demand.

The correlation between figures: 1 and 2 [3] indicates that almost all developed countries have made investments in social programs, which are targeted programs to help low-income and vulnerable populations. Nonetheless, the degree of investment in these programs varies substantially in different countries, as they are mentioned in [6] and [7].

This research reveals an in-depth approach to social welfare policies, which need to be widely understood in society. Further details on the adopted methodology can be found in many fields of social policy, supranational problems did not manifest themselves to such an extent that international solutions were needed, as we can understand in [8] and [9].

Based on this study, social welfare policies promote an innovative and in-depth discussion of its power in society. This approach suggests that with the insertion of globalization and capitalist practices, social welfare policies are the mainstream for coping with the inequalities caused by these transformations while serving for the continuity of social progress. What is striking here is the surprising effects that these policies bring to global society. In addition, it is essential to associate social welfare policies with current cultural, scientific, and social transformations, which are increasingly enhancing international relations.

This volume may be helpful primarily to conceptually those who wish to understand the workings of the social welfare policies and its effects on international relations. It might also be useful to those who are interested in knowing the practices of social welfare policies in global interactions and how they have contributed to the enhancement of social progress in contemporary times. This paper fills in this gap, it offers a new perspective on social welfare policies by thoroughly analyzing its effects on the development of global relations. This work examines how we can use social welfare to understand the relevant social transformations, as well as investigates how their characteristics directly affect multilateral relations.

The rest of the research is organized as follows: Introduction discusses the origin and importance of social welfare policies and their relationship with global development. In order to support this information, we used data from figures 1 and 2 [3],[4] regarding the priority of social welfare policies and the division of their levels of investment around the world. Methodology and Development validate the role of social policies and exemplifies data showing the implications on the practices of these policies around the world. The Results determine the principles and impacts of social welfare policies, such as: the process of internationalization and cultural integration through the action of international practices. Other processes were mentioned in this context, for instance: transnationalism, social impact jobs, and sustainable

development. The conclusion confirms the results of an international perspective in social welfare policies.

2. Research Methods

This paper provides new insights into the impact of social welfare policies on global relations, as it is well known the importance of social welfare policies to address inequalities, defend and guarantee the rights of the ruling class.

An interesting aspect that emerged from the analysis is the implications of social welfare policies around the world, as well as the perspectives on social welfare policies and possible contributions they can bring to the world. The most significant aspect of the data was the correlation between social welfare policies and international relations. [6] In order to understand the process of social welfare policies, a series of analyzes were performed. This method represents a viable alternative to explain their practices in the world through the data and information prepared by international organizations. These results broaden our understanding of the impact of social welfare policies on international relations, constituted in favor of social, cultural, and political development.

2.1 Methodology and Development

Firstly, the approach is mainly based on how social welfare policies work and its effects on society. Data were collected following the [3] and [4] method. The outcomes of this trial will have serious implications for the development of social welfare policies, which are constantly established to strengthen international relations and practices in modern times.

The study of social welfare policies is attracting attention because of its association with the social, cultural, and global relations. For this reason, we might not analyze this research in a simplistic way, otherwise it can be misinterpreted. The results can be demonstrated by evaluating the impacts of social welfare policies on a global scale and understanding how much they are needed to address inequalities and improve the well-being of communities. [9]

In addition, data were obtained using international analysis on social welfare policies, demonstrating how they are being evaluated in countries and continents, as how well as their perspectives are represented in society. This work has revealed that social welfare policies imply the maintenance of governments to make social progress while generating advances in the international scenario. As stated by Midgley [1], Marx and Engels augmented these developments by arguing that global prosperity could be achieved if the world's industrial workers unite against capitalist exploitation. Although the word international can be interpreted

narrowly as inter-nation state in that it only involves interactions between people in different countries, activities that promote wellbeing also operate at the global level.

Interestingly, we must reveal other occurrences such as: transnationalism, the new practices of international organizations, the trend of "Social Impact Jobs" and sustainable development, which can be considered the effects of social welfare policies on international scenario. These effects signal the need for additional studies on contributions resulting from the correlation between social welfare policies and multilateral relations.

With the advent of globalization, new problems emerged regarding the social inequality, consequently, social welfare policies were increasingly expanded more widely throughout the world to mitigate the effects of these adversities. In their widely acclaimed work, Michie et.al. [10] assumed that there is an association between the growth of transnationalism and social welfare policies. Further, Milsom [11] offered a comprehensive overview of the emergence of new social jobs, the so-called "Social impact jobs", arising from the social welfare policies, allow greater social inclusion, in addition to a greater understanding of social problems and the environment, through the theme of social and sustainable development that are increasingly present in society.

The 2015 paper by Teodorescu [12], for instance, is known for its careful analysis of the sustainable development. We can understand that her observations further corroborate that it is important to have an efficient formulation of social welfare policies, which are responsible for bringing these ideas of social progress.

Moreover, both national and international popular organizations are also widely recognized as necessary to this theme, as they are responsible for formulating and implementing these social welfare policies while simultaneously promoting and reinforcing the importance of these policies to global development. As a consequence of practices of these organizations in relation to social welfare policies, processes such as: internationalization and cultural integration become more common in society. [13]

2.2 The influence of social welfare policies on international practices

Transnacionalism	International organizations
Internationalization	Social impact trends
Cultural integration	Sustainable development

Table 1 - The elements which come from the relationship between social welfare policies and the globalization process

Fig. 3 - The main effects of social welfare policies around the world

Fig. 4 - Cycle of social welfare policies conflicts

3. Results

Given these analyses from the relationship between figures: 3, 4 and table 1, we perceived that social welfare policies are regarded as the main factors in analyzing current international trends that have become more popular due to the need to understand their actions in society, in the face of unequal development resulting from the process of capitalism and globalization. In fact, they are also the responsible for the advance of new transformations which positively impact global transformations. These results may be interpreted with care, because we are analyzing many impacts of social policies on the world from a brief and widespread perspective. However, given the small sample size, caution must be used, as it is a specific theme that involves different factors associated with social welfare policies. In this case, this study should be reflected in a multilateral perspective due to its broad and international approach. Midgley's work [1] has made a significant contribution to the thematic by presenting the realities of global social welfare and its aspects to improve social welfare in an

international overview.

The results of this study determined that developed countries have made major investments in social welfare policies than less developed countries. The difference of results between developed and undeveloped countries is mainly due to the greater investments of social programs formulated by developed countries to improve the quality of life of their populations, as we can understand in [3] and [4]. The findings support hypothesis that developed countries could be expected to be more committed to the development of social welfare policies than less developed ones. Conversely, there is a need for social programs in less developed countries so that this disparity can be less significant and unequal. Results also confirm that social well-being has evolved at a time when countries are concerned with basic human needs, since the greater the organization and implementation strategy, the better the impact of the social welfare policy on multilateral relations.

To sum up, these international comparisons were made thanks to the results that confirm how much the social welfare policies are necessary for global development. The study provides the case for a new way of understand social welfare policies in equal ways around the world. These results broaden our understanding of positive impact of social welfare policies in different countries, due to their priorities, needs, and investments, as well as understanding the representations of their practices and conflicts in society through illustrative figures: 3, 4 and table 1 which indicate the causes responsible for the impacts of this theme, addressed in the references [8] - [13]. These findings suggest the following direction for future research, considering that social welfare policies must be analyzed and understood in depth, since they play a crucial role in the formation of societies, namely, they are increasingly acting in international relations in favor of a prosperous and transformative development for the future.

4. Conclusions

Therefore, a discussion of the impact of social welfare policies on international relations was essential to understand the functions these policies perform for the well-being of international communities, since social welfare policies face inequalities, and act in the defense of the rights of the ruling class. This approach developed an in-depth study to exemplify the contributions of social welfare policies in global interactions and applies this data set to prove the benefits which these policies bring to the social progress.

In summary, the impacts of social welfare policies on international relations have been increasingly analyzed in the current scenario, as it has become a topic of great interest for the development of new strategies to reduce inequality arising from capitalism. The present study has, to the greatest extent, examined the social welfare policies from a

historical and global approach.

Overall, these results suggest that new global trends, for example: transnationalism, social impact jobs and sustainable development are the main impacts generated by social welfare policies. As discussed, in this study, we have presented the internationalization and cultural integration that provides support from international organizations which are responsible for the process of developing these policies around the world. To conclude, this paper has shown the effects of social welfare policies on international relations. This is a key area to be explored further, while future research should also consider the potential effects of social welfare policies from an international perspective.

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